

D7.1: Monitoring and Evaluation Guide

TRANSFORM

Deliverable description

Deliverable:

D7.1 Monitoring and Evaluation Guide

Due date:

30/09/2020

Actual submission date:

12/07/2021

Project start date:

01/01/2020

Duration:

36 Months

Work Package concerned:

WP7 - Monitoring and Evaluation

Concerned work package leader:

University of Bergen

Dissemination level:

PU: Public (must be available on the website)

CO: Confidential, only for members of the consortium (including the Commission Services)

CI: Classified, as referred to in Commission Decision 2001/844/EC

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Revision history:

Version 1.0: submitted on 04/11/2020

Version 1.1: revised version submitted on 12/07/2021 implementing modifications requested during the first project review process

Statement of originality

This submission is the work of the authors and has by the date of submission not been submitted or published elsewhere.

Disclaimer

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This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under the grant agreement N° 872687

Summary

TRANSFORM is a coordination and support action funded under the SwafS-14 call topic of Horizon 2020 to help implement the principles and practices of RRI – Responsible Research and Innovation – into institutions, policies and practices of innovation at the regional scale. To this effect, the project involves itself in processes of innovation, policy-making and practice in three European regions: Lombardy, Catalonia and the Brussels-Capital region, our so-called “clusters”. The project initiatives include efforts to introduce RRI approaches into S3 policies in the three regions.

Implementation of RRI or any other approach should come with a strategy for monitoring and evaluating the progress of that approach. This deliverable, D7.1, is the first version of the main strategic document of WP7, namely “TRANSFORM’s Monitoring and Evaluation Guide”. As such it reports the results from project task 7.1 “Mapping of TRANSFORM’s ecosystem of monitoring and evaluation practices” and the first results from project task 7.2 “Design of TRANSFORM’s own suite of monitoring and evaluation activities”. Task 7.1 showed that while there is no shortage of proposed RRI indicators and monitoring practices suggested in the literature, relatively little is done at the regional level, or even fit for use at the regional level. There is, however, a firm commitment in the three TRANSFORM regions to implement RRI in their innovation policies, and with this commitment comes the need for monitoring and to some extent also indicators. D7.1 analyses the needs for monitoring and evaluation in terms of the set of different purposes that such monitoring and evaluation will have, and in terms of the types of causal narratives (“theories of change”) that are relevant for the project actions. The outcome of this analysis is a set of possible monitoring practices, indicators and success criteria for each type of purpose. This set includes monitoring of RRI learning as double-loop learning; a place-based version of the AREA framework for responsible innovation; a design for monitoring innovation for the common good by use of Boltanski’s and Thévenot’s theory of orders of worth; and the use of typologies for the quality of public participation. In sum, this provides TRANSFORM with a menu from which the consortium will continue to choose and co-create the actual monitoring practices and indicators of choice.

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Introduction to the Deliverable

TRANSFORM is a coordination and support action funded under the SwafS-14 call topic of Horizon 2020 to help implement the principles and practices of RRI – Responsible Research and Innovation – into institutions, policies and practices of innovation at the regional scale. To this effect, the project involves itself in processes of innovation, policy-making and practice in three European regions: Lombardy, Catalonia and the Brussels-Capital region, our so-called “clusters”. The project initiatives include efforts to introduce RRI approaches into S3 policies in the three regions.

Implementation of RRI or any other approach should come with a strategy for monitoring and evaluating the progress of that approach. TRANSFORM has a separate work package, WP7, dedicated to Monitoring and Evaluation, which operates in close interaction with another key strategic WP of the project, WP2. This deliverable, D7.1, is the first version of the main strategic document of WP7, namely TRANSFORM’s Monitoring and Evaluation Guide. As such it reports the results from project task 7.1 “Mapping of TRANSFORM’s ecosystem of monitoring and evaluation practices” and the first results from project task 7.2 “Design of TRANSFORM’s own suite of monitoring and evaluation activities”.

The University of Bergen has been the partner responsible for the preparation of the deliverable, while the entire consortium and our many collaborators in the three clusters have played an important role in providing valuable inputs, comments and edits along the way, through formal and informal consultations. In particular, we are grateful for the advice from our Advisory Board.

There is no shortage of academic treatises and policy reports on monitoring and evaluation practices and indicators for RRI. This document does not aim to comprehensively represent or replace that literature. Rather, we have tried to provide a concise and succinct treatment with focus on the specific challenges for TRANSFORM and the concrete methodological decisions to be made in this project.

Outline of TRANSFORM's Needs for Monitoring and Evaluation

In the course of the first months of the project, TRANSFORM has developed its strategic planning by regular WP2-WP7 joint work meetings (held online because of the COVID-19 pandemic). One of the early results of this process is a more precise description of the various project goals and purposes for which there is a need for monitoring and evaluation activities. Concretely, we have identified five distinct (but not mutually exclusive) goals and purposes:

1. TRANSFORM WP7 should develop and carry out continuous monitoring practices in real time for “ongoing normative assessment” and learning within the project and in close interaction with WP2. This is a contribution to project *development* (mutual learning). It corresponds to WP7 Task 7.3 and will be undertaken in close collaboration with WP2.
2. TRANSFORM should perform an assessment of its own project activities, outputs and outcomes, with due attention to the requirements of the Grant Agreement and the SwafS-14 call. This is our own project *evaluation* proper. It corresponds to WP7 Task 7.4 and is primarily an independent activity within the TRANSFORM project.
3. TRANSFORM should provide an analysis of impact pathways and “benefits” of TRANSFORM activities, in line with the requirements of the SwafS-14 call. It corresponds to WP7 Task 7.5.
4. TRANSFORM may offer RRI indicators and monitoring/evaluation practices and frameworks to be used by the regional/territorial actors with whom we interact, as a contribution to implement RRI into Smart Specialisation Strategies. This would be a project *output* not explicitly mentioned in the WP7 description but still clearly anticipated in the DoA.
5. In the same vein, TRANSFORM may offer RRI indicators and monitoring/evaluation practices as a contribution to implement RRI into other regional/territorial innovation activities/innovation policy activities than the S3 strategy processes. This would also be a project *output* that is anticipated in the DoA but not explicitly mentioned in the WP7 description.

The aim of this document is to provide written guidance on *how* to proceed to meet these goals and purposes. We emphasize that we distinguish between these different purposes for analytical and methodological reasons, beginning with the “*why*” in order to move to the “*how*”. In practice, however, the purposes will be overlapping and we expect that some monitoring and evaluation practices and indicators will be able to serve multiple purposes at the same time.

TRANSFORM

Mapping of TRANSFORM’s Ecosystem of Monitoring and Evaluation Practices (WP7 Task 7.1)

The first task of WP7 is to map and take stock of what already is being done (by others and by members of our consortium and our regional clusters) in terms of relevant monitoring and evaluation practices. This task was also anticipated by the original call for proposals because there is a need to avoid duplication of efforts and build on existing information and knowledge.

The stock-taking exercise has been performed by desk research and by individual and group consultations with members of the consortium, regional clusters and advisory board in addition to selected experts. Specifically, designated interviews were performed with representatives of the regional authorities participating in TRANSFORM. In addition, TRANSFORM, together with the SwafS-14-funded project SeeRRI as well as the “over-arching” SwafS RIA SuperMoRRI, made an initiative to liaise and exchange experiences with the entire group of SwafS-14-funded actions.

Unfortunately but not surprisingly, the result is that there is relatively little data collection or ongoing monitoring/evaluation inside the relevant innovation ecosystems with direct relevance to any of the goals and purposes laid out above. Specifically, we have almost no evidence of RRI monitoring or evaluation as such in the innovation ecosystems involved in TRANSFORM, also because they are planning to implement RRI thoroughly in their R&I governance and policy thanks to TRANSFORM. While this fact provides little support it can also be seen as an opportunity to create *de novo* designs and practices fit for purpose. Below we detail these results.

a) The Smart Specialisation Platform.

TRANSFORM directs its actions towards policies and practices that are related to Smart Specialisation Strategies in our three regions. JRC (European Commission-Joint Research Centre) is given the mandate to support the regions with data and advice through the Smart Specialisation Platform (S3 Platform). In addition, DG GROW has commissioned a regional version of the European Innovation Scoreboard, called the Regional Innovation Scoreboard. These initiatives produce data on the socio-economic variables of the innovation system (output, human resources, some structural conditions). They do not include RRI indicators or variables that could be used as inputs for existing RRI indicators or, to our knowledge, RRI-oriented monitoring or evaluation practices.

In one of its many technical reports on S3, the JRC proposed (report 03/2014) that regional benchmarking could include indicators on “institutions and values” but the indicators proposed were highly general (e.g., population surveys on statements such as “It is important to try new and different things in life” and “Most people can be trusted”). In a given case where long-term impact is considered, it is not unthinkable that data of the innovation scoreboard type could be relevant as result indicators. They are unlikely to be relevant, though, for any of the monitoring and evaluation purposes of TRANSFORM. TRANSFORM will maintain an active relationship to the JRC¹ for updates on methodological developments and will pursue an active dialogue with DG Regio as the responsible DG for S3 but so far there is no risk of duplication of efforts and no existing data to draw on for TRANSFORM’s monitoring and evaluation purposes.

b) The regional clusters of TRANSFORM

As far as we have been able to ascertain, there are few existing monitoring and evaluation practices or data collection in the three regional clusters (Lombardy, Catalonia and the Brussels region) of direct relevance to the TRANSFORM monitoring and evaluation needs and purposes. However, there are several relevant initiatives to which TRANSFORM can and will align. In Lombardy, there is a firm commitment to include the principle of RRI as an objective of its upcoming S3 plan, anchored in the inclusion of RRI in regional innovation legislation. This commitment entails the necessity of developing and including adequate monitoring. Furthermore, the Steering group for the regional innovation plan in the Brussels-Capital Region has done a survey as part of the process to renew the S3 plan for the region. The survey may contain data that can inform efforts to develop indicators and monitoring practices in TRANSFORM. The main objective of the survey is to engage stakeholders and the wider public in identifying opportunities for social, organizational, technological and other innovations to meet societal challenges, including soliciting imaginative out-of-the-box ideas to what new challenges the region should focus on and visions of desired futures.² Finally, there is an ongoing initiative in GenCat, la Generalitat de Catalunya, to map changes in innovation collaboration networks as an indicator of RRI performance. This initiative is relevant to our needs and purposes and TRANSFORM will develop its collaboration with GenCat on this issue.

Furthermore, we expect rapid development in the situation of the three clusters in the following months and years as regional innovation agendas and S3 plans are being revised and renewed;

¹ JRC representatives involved in the S3 activities intervened at the TRANSFORM Kick-off meeting (held on-line on 3 March, 2020) and further collaborations along the course of the project were envisaged on that occasion.

² <https://innoviris.brussels/news/enquete-plan-regional-dinnovation>

indeed, our contact with and involvement in these processes is an opportunity to achieve TRANSFORM project goals.

c) RRI monitoring and evaluation - State of the Art

The academic and policy-related literature on RRI is rapidly growing and there is no scarcity of suggestions and proposals for how to monitor and evaluate RRI initiatives and/or states of affair. In addition to the MoRRI indicators³ and the EC Expert Group on Indicators (Strand et al. 2015), there are numerous research papers dealing with the subject (notably Wickson and Carew 2014). Von Schomberg and Hankins (2019) have published their extensive international handbook on responsible innovation, and later this year (2020), the handbook “Assessment of Responsible Innovation” is expected to be released (Yaeghmaei & van de Poel, forthcoming). In addition, the SuperMoRRI project is advancing as arguably the lighthouse of research on RRI monitoring and evaluation within the SwafS programme, and also with a special responsibility to coordinate efforts in this regard within the SwafS ecosystem.

A critical observation, however, is that few proposed indicators and monitoring and evaluation practices have been validated or comprehensively tested. Some of them have not been tested at all, and none of them have been validated for use in a regional innovation ecosystem.

Worse, there is no stable “reality” of RRI against which the indicators can be validated. What RRI “really” means, is contested, and the disagreements reflect deep differences in opinions on how R&I systems work and how they ought to work⁴. To simplify the point, RRI was originally introduced by von Schomberg as a policy principle to solve the Collingridge Dilemma: That new technology sometimes creates social and environmental harm in surprising and unpredictable ways, and that by the time we know, it is too late to get rid of it. RRI was in this sense an attempt at adding another element of governance to innovation processes, not as a “fourth hurdle” but as a societal shaping of them. However, when Horizon 2020 introduced RRI as a cross-cutting principle, this happened within the broader policy context of Europe 2020 which aimed at speeding up innovation. Within that context, however, RRI tends to be imagined as a contribution to the acceleration of innovation by improving social relevance and acceptance. While there is no intrinsic contradiction between the

³ <http://morri-project.eu/>

⁴ https://www.super-morri.eu/super-morri/more/blog/blog_article3.php

goals of steering and accelerating innovation, there is no doubt that scholarly as well as policy-related RRI literature provides ample documentation of the tensions between the two goals.

RRI indicators and monitoring approaches is a venue for the continued struggle over what RRI should mean. Rather than seeing RRI indicators as attempts at faithfully portraying the reality of RRI, one can see them as means to create or consolidate the meaning of RRI and to influence the ways in which policy is implemented. For instance, if we insist on quantitative RRI indicators that are statistically robust, this will favour the gender equality key of RRI, simply because this is the single RRI dimension for which there is solid quantitative data. Furthermore, it will imply a focus on gender equality as measured by demographic and socio-economic data on the workforce (which is easy to measure) and not as measured as gender bias in research problem definitions (which is very hard to measure).

To add to the challenges, most existing indicators either focuses on the country level (e.g. MoRRI indicators) or on the individual Research Performing Organisation / Research Funding Organisation / Research Project level (e.g. Wickson & Carew 2014). The regional/territorial level, or indeed the R&I ecosystem level at all, is generally not much considered.

To sum up, there are useful ideas in the literature but they cannot be pulled off the shelf for TRANSFORM purposes without a close consideration of what purpose the indicator or monitoring practice was intended for, and what descriptive and normative background assumptions it is based upon. But that also means that TRANSFORM has to identify and make explicit our own background assumptions and intentions in order to make the choices. Further, in order for TRANSFORM to develop indicators and monitoring practices for sustainable Smart specialisation strategies, we will need to develop a conception of RRI that is suitable for regional innovation, and that can at the same time be captured by indicators or specific monitoring practices.

d) The SwafS-14 Actions and SuperMoRRI

As we are in continuous contact with SuperMoRRI, with the TRANSFORM coordinator being part of the advisory board of SuperMoRRI and the University of Bergen being partner in both TRANSFORM and SuperMoRRI, we closely follow the developments and results from that latter project. As of September 2020, however, there are no results from SuperMoRRI that have direct bearing on the methodological choices that TRANSFORM currently have to make.

TRANSFORM, together with SeeRRI and SuperMoRRI, recently launched an initiative to collaborate with the whole group of SwafS-14 Actions (including also CHERRIES, DigiTeRRI, RRI2SCALE, TeRRifica, TeRRitoria and TetRRIs) to exchange views and experiences on monitoring and evaluation and, if possible, look for synergies and collaborations. A previous project, SISCODE, has also been mentioned as relevant as its scope was highly similar to the SwafS-14 topic, of implementing RRI in regional innovation processes⁵. Two online meetings have taken place, and SuperMoRRI has offered to host bimonthly meetings with the SwafS-14 group as well as access to and support with the upcoming SuperMoRRI self-evaluation tool. TRANSFORM will continue to play an active part in this process.

⁵ <https://siscodeproject.eu/>

Design of TRANSFORM's Own Suite of Monitoring and Evaluation Activities: Monitoring and Evaluation versus Indicator Development and Deployment

The implication from the results of Task 7.1 is that TRANSFORM has many degrees of freedom in its design of monitoring and evaluation activities. There is no risk of duplication of effort and no clear guidance on best practice in the context of territorial innovation.

In discussions on these issues, within TRANSFORM as elsewhere, the issue often becomes one of selecting *indicators*. In this regard it is important to recall that there are many ways to monitor and evaluate activities and states of affairs. Indicators are only one type of tools, and it is in principle wholly possible to monitor and evaluate without using indicators.

Indicators are guides for *certain types of action*. To quote Theodore Porter, a world-leading historian of statistics, “Etymologically, and indicator, like an index, has to do with pointing. [...] indicators detect, point or measure, but do not explain. [...] A quantitative index or indicator typically cannot measure the very thing of interest, but in its place something whose movements show a consistent relationship to that thing. Since its purpose is merely to indicate as a guide to action, ease of measurement is preferred to meaning or depth.” (Porter 2015, p.34)

Often, indicators (Porter continues) are “pursued to promote informed action and decisions of a decentralized sort.” Historically, they were created to efficiently provide information at a distance to decision-makers who lack first-hand knowledge.

This point has direct implications on our methodological choices. For Task 7.3 and 7.4, which correspond to our own intra-project learning process and project evaluation, respectively, we have first-hand knowledge and there is little need for indicators. For the analysis of impact pathways (Task 7.5) we are expected to produce understanding and explanations from which indicators eventually could be constructed. Yet, the TRANSFORM project takes place within a larger institutional context of Horizon 2020 and DG RTD, within which there is a need to develop adequate monitoring practices in order to promote and oversee the implementation of RRI in terms of the KPI of the SwafS programme, “institutional change”. It is in this context that MoRRI indicators and SDGs are mentioned as part of the logic of intervention, which places emphasis on the value of accountability.

Our intention to help regional actors implementing RRI in S3 by offering them, *inter alia*, RRI indicators (or at least an RRI indicator co-creation process), is particularly interesting in this regard. In this case, regional actors are *not* external decision-makers who have to act at a distance without first-hand knowledge. They are actors *inside* their system. However, their need for indicators can have various origins. First, they are also part of a larger institutional context where they have to provide information to decision-makers at a distance (for instance within the European Commission). Accordingly, indicators can be an efficient way for them to document and justify that they fulfil the S3 enabling condition. Secondly, while the historical origin of indicators was the need for effective transfer of information across physical distance, there are also many other types of distance, including the intellectual and cognitive distance between types of expertise. RRI indicators may compensate for informational disadvantage among decision-makers *about* RRI *within* the region. Furthermore, within institutional contexts such as that of public administrations, indicators may hold value both as symbolic capital and as vehicles for action (Turnhout et al. 2014). To introduce indicators in such circumstances does not come without risks, though, especially because RRI is a relatively new concept without a long institutional track record. RRI experts may think that RRI is no less meaningful than, say, GDP, or economic growth as a proxy for welfare and well-being. In practice, however, new concepts need a stronger justification than old and consolidated ones. The implication is that regional actors are not likely to adopt RRI principles and practices for long if they do not properly understand them, in which case they will acquire first-hand knowledge.

The conclusion from this paragraph is that we are likely to need a mixed and balanced suite of indicators and other monitoring and evaluation approaches to fulfil the full set of goals and purposes as defined above. Tasks 7.3-7.5/goals 1-3 (p. 3-4 above) are likely to be better off by qualitative monitoring and evaluation approaches. For goals 4-5, at least some indicators are likely to be needed.

Design: The Choice of RRI Concept and Framework

A conclusion from the entire discussion above is that TRANSFORM also needs to define, at least in a quite general sense, its own position with regard to RRI. The answer to “how to monitor RRI?” depends on “why monitor RRI?”, which again depends on “why RRI?” and “what is RRI?” These higher-level questions have different legitimate answers and can only be answered by a consortium as ours by making a *decision*. TRANSFORM makes such decisions by discussing them in the project meetings at cluster and consortium levels and conferring with its advisory board. Our position is:

- a. TRANSFORM embraces a broad understanding of RRI. It includes the so-called 5 or 6 keys or policy issues of the European Commission, and also R&I policy and practice efforts to contribute to substantive values such as social justice, inclusion, and sustainability as broadly conceived (and therefore a *more social and greener* Europe). This choice is in line with the EC Expert Group on RRI indicators (Strand et al. 2015) and in line with the overarching goals of Europe 2020 and the European Green Deal and builds on previous work among partners in the consortium⁶.
- b. TRANSFORM furthermore endorses the “AREA” (*anticipate, reflect, engage, act*) understanding of the process dimension of RRI (as originally developed by UK scholars such as Owen, Stilgoe, MacNaghten). In this way TRANSFORM aligns itself with previous notable SwafS actions such as RRITools and RRI-PRACTICE in seeing the “keys” and the AREA framework as complementary dimensions that deal with R&I policy issues and R&I process dimensions, respectively. In this regard, TRANSFORM will build on Fitjar, Benneworth and Asheim (2019) to make the AREA framework “place-based” and apply it in an S3 context.
- c. In terms of the policy keys, TRANSFORM focuses on *public engagement and governance*, and has less structured actions on science education, gender equality and ethics, even if initiatives dealing with these concepts could be part of the broader approach of the 3 territories on implementing RRI. Within the ethics “key” emphasis will be placed on societal relevance and ethical acceptability, rather than research integrity and protection of research objects due to the centrality of the policymaking actors in this project and their performances (policies). Open access is becoming obsolete as an RRI key, while we see convergences between RRI and open science and to some extent open innovation (though the latter in practice also to a large extent translates to the “key” of public engagement).

⁶ <http://projectsmartmap.eu/>; <http://magic-nexus.eu/>

- d. Finally, as a group of researchers, and as a group of clusters, TRANSFORM should expect and tolerate a diversity of descriptive and normative background assumptions on what problems RRI is meant to solve, and how it solves them. For instance, we do not need a consensus on the policy narratives of RRI as a solution to the Collingridge dilemma or a contribution to acceleration of innovation. In both cases we can agree on the purpose of RRI to contribute to *the common good* and to the need to better align the development of science and technology with the values, needs and concerns of society.

We are now ready to revisit the various purposes for monitoring and evaluation.

Design: Defining the Object of Monitoring and Evaluation

The TRANSFORM DoA presents the following simplified causal narrative (Figure 1):

Figure 1

In order to implement our monitoring and evaluation tasks, the causal narrative has to be refined while still not become overly complicated. A slightly refined alternative would be:

1. As far as WP7 is concerned, the TRANSFORM process begins with the set of actions that are RRI initiatives and *tasks within the project, performed by staff who work for the project*. We will call these actions “TRANSFORM actions” and the immediate result of the actions are in this sense *project outputs* (not to be conflated with “outputs” in the sense of project dissemination products).
2. The next step of the TRANSFORM process is that these TRANSFORM actions create effects in the regional clusters. For instance, they could influence the existence and content of innovation pilots or of innovation policy-making processes. They could also have effects on the actors in the regional clusters, for instance on RRI competence and/or awareness, or by creating or expanding networks of such actors. In project evaluation terminology, these effects are *project outcomes*.
3. In the next step, the actors in the regional clusters perform actions such as making RRI initiatives in their regional R&I ecosystem. Examples are revisions of regional innovation policies, the inclusion of RRI elements in RIS3 plans, and also processes that may or not may fall under point 2 above, such as innovation pilots, competence building, etc. In project evaluation terminology, the results of these actions belong to the class of *project impacts*. The actions are envisaged by our DoA but are not in the strict sense TRANSFORM project actions. In practice, however, there will be no absolute dichotomy between outcomes and impacts in TRANSFORM because there will be pilots and other initiatives that will be undertaken as a collaboration between TRANSFORM actors and regional actors with which

we are in a process of interaction (see also the double causal pathway below from yellow to green boxes).

- Some of the impacts under 3, notably RIS3 plans and other regional innovation policies and agendas, will be in need of documentation and monitoring in their own institutional context in the clusters, or vis-a-vis EU institutions or other decision-makers who act at a (physical or cognitive) distance.

We may depict this causal narrative as follows:

Figure 2

We may map the goals and purposes, enumerated from 1 to 5 on page 3-4, as follows:

Figure 3

In the remainder of the deliverable, we outline what we find to be suitable conceptual and methodological frameworks for the goals and purposes 1-5.

Purpose 1. How to Improve TRANSFORM? Ongoing Monitoring of Outputs.

TRANSFORM WP7 needs to develop and carry out continuous monitoring practices in real time for “ongoing normative assessment” and learning within the project and in close interaction with WP2.

This is perhaps the most straight-forward task of WP7 as it involves a lively interaction with WP2, an interaction we already entertain. The main question about the theory of change here is: “How do we TRANSFORM project actors interact with regional actors as well as we can?”

We propose a focus on *RRI learning*, based on Hesjedal et al (2020)’s study on RRI learning as requiring double-loop learning, and Mejlgaard et al (2018)’s study on RRI learning as a matter of developing practical wisdom (phronesis) and critical reflection. This is highly compatible with the AREA framework as well as some of the indicator items of Wickson and Carew (2014).

Double-loop learning can be defined as learning that involves the questioning and revision of elements of one’s own world-view. This can happen gradually or also take place as crucial moments: “I never thought of this before!” In the context of RRI, it can involve the doubt or breakdown of commonsensical or uncritical beliefs about science, truth, authority, expertise, technology, the functioning of the market, et cetera.

Implementation of this point is quite straightforward: The already established WP2-WP7 forum has frequent meetings, and the monitoring can take place in these meetings, supported with written documentation. This should include:

- Participants from the WP7 leader (UiB) take field notes from WP2-WP7 forum meetings
- WP7 leader is provided with documentation of webinars and with copies of written documentation whenever that is prepared for purposes of WP2 and WP3-5 tasks
- Cluster leaders provide suitably deidentified/anonymized access to minutes, field notes and diary entries from cluster meetings and other relevant cluster interactions
- WP7 leader performs regular semi-structured interviews with cluster leaders and selected cluster participants
- WP7 contributes to the mutual learning processes and capacity building actions envisaged and organised by WP2

Purpose 2 and 4/5. A Place-Based Version of the AREA Framework.

As noted above, a promising resource for analysing and understanding RRI-related needs in smart specialization is Fitjar, Benneworth and Asheim (2019) on the integration of RRI with RIS3. The integrative table below is borrowed from their article and shows how the authors envisage the integration of the four dimensions of RRI defined by Stilgoe et al. (2013) with the stages of smart specialization processes identified in the RIS3 guide (Foray et al. 2012).

Table 2. Integration of responsible innovation and smart specialisation processes

		Stages of the smart specialisation process					
		Analysis	Governance	Vision	Prioritisation	Policy mix	Monitoring
Dimensions of RRI	Anticipation	Identify societal needs	Identify all potential stakeholders	Consider potential negative or unintended outcomes	Consider impact of priorities on social and environmental outcomes	Consider unintended outcomes of policy	Evaluate broader effects, beyond narrow policy aims
	Reflexivity	Reflect on value system on which analysis is based	Consider potentially diverging interests and reflect on differences in power	Allow for different perspectives on vision for future	Reflect on impact beyond the represented stakeholders—and beyond the region	Reflect on diverging interests for different policy mixes	Reflect on value system of evaluators
	Inclusion	Engage stakeholders in analysis	Include a variety of stakeholders in management	Include a variety of visions and opinions	Have an open process around prioritisation where different voices are heard	Keep policy-making in democratic for a	Include stakeholders in evaluation
	Responsiveness	Respond to new knowledge and other perspectives	Respect all opinions, including from minority and less powerful groups	Be responsive to critical concerns about the vision	Allow for criticism of prioritisation and accept that chosen priorities may be wrong	Let dissenting voices be heard	Allow for change in evaluation criteria and results in response to feedback

Table 1. Reproduced from Fitjar et al. (2019)

Fitjar et al. argue that an integration will have the double benefit of sensitising RRI to local contexts as well as opening up smart specialization to broader societal interests. In TRANSFORM we may use this integrated framework as a basis from which to articulate relevant elicitation-questions for monitoring and evaluation practices. While Fitjar et al focus on the conceptual and theoretical possibilities for an integration with RIS3, TRANSFORM is based on the premise that the actors’ own assessment how RRI can be integrated is the focus of interest, not the ex ante construction of a prêt à porter value matrix. Building on Fitjar et al we propose to transform the imperatives above into questions that are meaningful in entrepreneurial development contexts and that may aid the “translation” of RRI into the target domain. Something along the lines of:

- Given the success criteria for entrepreneurial development, will engaging more societal actors in the EDP (entrepreneurial discovery process) add to the chances of success in this case? What are the main reasons for the relevance/irrelevance of more engagement? How could engaging more societal actors add to the chances of success (example)?
- Will inclusion of more actors and stakeholders in the EDP increase chances of anticipating opportunities and obstacles. What is the main reason for your view? How could engaging more actors contribute to the anticipation of opportunities and obstacles (example)?
- Will the success of the EDP depend on the ability to listen and respond to input from from other actors and stakeholders? What is the main reason for your view? If yes, how could the chances of success increase (example)?

These questions are meant only as examples, and it can be a meaningful exercise for co-creation processes in the clusters (with regard to pilots and other initiatives “in green” in the figures above) to go through the table, prioritise or choose among its squares, and formulate concrete criteria and questions that help ascertain whether the criteria are met. This is clearly relevant to purpose 2, that of evaluating TRANSFORM outcomes and cluster activity outcomes. Clusters could also come to decide that such questions should be included as (non-standard) criteria or indicators for purpose 4-5, that is, for documentation intended for decision-makers at a distance. In the latter case, an important design choice is who will answer the questions, for instance, external experts or selected citizens/stakeholders.

Purpose 2, 3 and 4/5: Innovation for the Common Good

We have already noticed that the idea of *common good* potentially communicates much easier than “RRI”, which is perceived as quite abstract. French sociologists Luc Boltanski and Laurent Thévenot (2006) identified six distinct conceptual frameworks from which people justify (or criticise) social action, bound together by shared values (or “economies of worth”). According to Boltanski and Thévenot, a notion of the common good is what ultimately grounds each order of justification and is also what has the potential for supporting agreement between different “worlds”.

Table 1 Orders of worth

	<i>Inspired</i>	<i>Domestic</i>	<i>Civic</i>	<i>Opinion</i>	<i>Market</i>	<i>Industrial</i>
Mode of evaluation (worth)	Grace, nonconformity, creativeness	Esteem, reputation	Collective interest	Renown	Price	Productivity, efficiency
Format of relevant information	Emotional	Oral, exemplary, anecdotal	Formal, official	Semiotic	Monetary	Measurable: criteria, statistics
Elementary relation	Passion	Trust	Solidarity	Recognition	Exchange	Functional link
Human qualification	Creativity, ingenuity	Authority	Equality	Celebrity	Desire, purchasing power	Professional competency, expertise

Table 2. Reproduced from Boltanski & Thévenot (1999)

The conceptual framework developed by Boltanski and Thévenot could prove useful for understanding arguments for or against the usefulness of a certain course of action, such as the choice of an innovation initiative, a goal for an innovation agenda, or even the choice of an RRI indicator. Furthermore, the framework can serve for reflecting on how the justification of these would change according to different “orders of worth”. For instance, the framework explains why arguments from say, the market order and arguments from the civic order will differ by showing that they are based on different ideas of the common good. The framework also offers clues to how agreement (although inherently fragile) can be achieved by articulating overarching notions of the common good that bridge orders of worth, at least temporarily. The idea here is simply that this is a useful framework for discussing what grounds legitimate conceptions of the common good, how and

why they differ, and how they sometimes can be reconciled. In this way, it is possible to engage citizens and stakeholders in deliberations on what is an important common good, and why.

We can see a range of possible applications of this conceptual framework. First, it can be applied in the RRI initiatives themselves, as a tool for deliberation. Secondly, it can be used as a quite simple and crude indicator (for Purpose 4/5), by classifying outcomes of participatory (and non-participatory processes) with regard to the dominating orders of worth. For instance, is it so that the market and industrial orders of worth are more dominant if citizens are not involved in innovation agenda-setting, while the civic order of worth becomes more dominant with citizen participation? This is an empirical question that can be assessed in the concrete case (though we suspect that the RRI literature tend somewhat naïvely to assume that the answer is affirmative). Thirdly, the framework can be used as a device in qualitative interviews for Purpose 2, the TRANSFORM project evaluation.

Purpose 2 and 4/5: Further Aspects of the Quality of Participation

Engagement, inclusion and participation is perhaps the most central dimension of RRI across the whole of the TRANSFORM project, and an important objective of WP7 is to make it possible to evaluate the quality of participation. Quality is key in this regard; counting the number of citizens involved in a given process is not meaningful.

The frameworks explained above can both be seen as relevant to assessing the quality of participation, in particular the “inclusion” row of the table from Fitjar et al. (2019). However, we propose to add additional elements after having considered the particular context of TRANSFORM.

The first element is that of the purpose of the owner of the participatory process when the owner is an institution endowed with power over the decision that the participatory process is directed towards. This seems to be the situation in most of the activities related to TRANSFORM; in this sense we may say that the participation is organised top-down and is not of the “grassroot” type. In such cases, Arnstein (1969) proposed a typology already 50 years ago, later called Arnstein’s ladder:

A Ladder of Citizen Participation, Arnstein, 1969

<http://lithgow-schmidt.dk/sherry-arnstein/ladder-of-citizen-participation.html>

Figure 4. The ladder of participation, originally from Arnstein (1969).

For the purpose of TRANSFORM, we would need to adapt Arnstein's ladder to a suitable form because Arnstein's normative view will hardly be able to be endorsed by the consortium. Essentially it implies that direct democracy is always better than representative democracy, bureaucracy and technocracy. In a less normative and tendentious version, though, the typology allows for a quick look into how a given participatory process is being perceived by the participants. It can even be used as an indicator. One can simply invite participants to score the participatory event or process on the ladder.

The second element is that of the product of the participation in, for example, a process of innovation agenda-setting. Two qualities important to RRI can be summarized by each their sentence:

- The outcome of the process incorporates and takes into account needs and concerns expressed by the participants.
- The participants' visions and imaginations of what would be a desirable future to them, are well incorporated in the outcome of the process.

The first sentence is very true to the EU definition of RRI while the second is in line with what arguably is the major recommendation from Jasanoff's scholarship on R&I policy-making and the importance of the coproduction of sociotechnical imaginaries (see e.g. Jasanoff & Kim 2009). For at least two of our regions (Lombardy and Brussels-Capital) it may be highly relevant to monitor the quality of processes of co-creation of imagined futures as a dimension of participatory agenda-setting processes.

These two qualities can be used in both qualitative and quantitative assessments, in qualitative interviews / unstructured questions or scorings on a Likert scale, respectively. Again, it would be important that the participants themselves or external and independent experts do the scoring if this is going to be used as indicators. Many variations can be conceived. For instance, one can easily define a process indicator by the question "Were citizens' visions and imaginations of what would be a desirable future for them, actively elicited and encouraged in the participatory process?" and so on. We anticipate a highly useful exchange of experience on such issues with the TRANSFORM partner in the US, CC-PES.

Purpose 4: RRI Monitoring as a Possible Contribution to Monitoring of the S3 Enabling Condition

With the completion of the first round of the S3 policy cycle, there is announced a change from *ex ante* approval to an approach where the regions continuously need to document that they successfully sustain S3 as “enabling condition” to access Cohesion Policy funds (good governance of S3).

Further work is needed by WP2 and WP7 to define the opportunities for RRI that might arise with this change. Three issues have been considered in this regard:

- What may be the easier and more likely opportunity for RRI in S3 is that with the requirement of documentation of the fulfilment of the enabling condition, there can be opportunities to introduce elements of RRI monitoring and/or indicators into the S3 plans *in the case that* RRI is introduced as a goal into the S3 plan in the first place. The provision of feasible RRI monitoring practices will make such an option more attractive and hence increase the chances of introducing RRI as a goal. As for the acceptability of RRI as an S3 goal, our preliminary analysis is that it indeed has become more acceptable due to the favourable policy trend towards participation in the OECD, which supports DG Regio in pilot actions for citizen engagement in Cohesion Policy and in the EU Commission policies (i.e. Conference of Europe promoted by the President Von der Leyen, EU Missions policy in Horizon Europe).
- In the work with this deliverable, we have considered the more involved option of trying to make the claim that RRI indeed can be seen as an instantiation of good governance, and suitable RRI indicators as a way to document good governance. Our conclusion so far, based on consultation within the consortium, including with our regional authorities and members of the advisory board, is negative: It seems at the moment unrealistic to try to frame RRI in this way. Still, we include the argument in the deliverable for future reference. The argument would run as follows: 19 years ago the European Commission defined good governance in terms of 5 basic principles: openness, participation, accountability, effectiveness and coherence.⁷ Since then, the context has changed. On one hand, there is a historical line from

⁷ <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/HR/TXT/?uri=LEGISSUM:l10109>

the White Paper on Good Governance to the Commission Recommendation for responsible nanosciences and nanotechnologies to the introduction of RRI. It is, however, a marginal line. The main trend went towards “SMART” objectives and NPM with a focus on accountability and effectiveness. According to the S3 Implementation Handbook, “good governance” simply means compliance to the plan, and process indicators are not even mentioned. Our preliminary conclusion is that this option is not viable as of today but it should be taken into account as a future possibility, especially if public participation gains further traction as a policy principle.

- Finally, we should monitor the possible implications on S3 policies in terms of the substantive values of sustainability and social justice as the European Green Deal calls for “a greener and more social Europe”. Indeed, suggestions have been made to move from S3 to “S4”, including the objective of sustainability into the scope of smart specialisation⁸. The effects this may have on regional policy within Europe remains to see.⁹ For regional clusters with an interest in this regard, however, TRANSFORM should be prepared to contribute with ideas for relevant RRI monitoring, e.g. by drawing on ideas from Strand et al. (2015).

⁸ https://ec.europa.eu/newsroom/jrcseville/item-detail.cfm?item_id=670313

⁹ <https://publications.jrc.ec.europa.eu/repository/handle/JRC121271>

Purpose 3: The Identification of TRANSFORM Impact Pathways and Evaluation of Impact

Evaluation of project impact within project lifetime is normally considered beyond project scope if not blatantly a contradiction in terms, since project impact normally is defined as what happens afterwards, as effects from project outcomes. Still, we have a contractual obligation to do our best in this regard, due to the proposal call text.

This task will be more meaningful in the second and third year of TRANSFORM and it will be detailed in the next version of the TRANSFORM Monitoring and Evaluation Guide. Figure 2 depicts our preliminary understanding of the task, namely to assemble monitoring and evaluation results along the causal narrative (or theory of change) for the project. The causal narrative is likely to be revised during project lifetime with subsequent adjustments to the monitoring and evaluation strategy.

On this point we will seek support from and synergy with the SuperMoRRI project, which includes a quite similar task in its WP5. Specifically, from our collaboration with the SuperMoRRI we know that that project is currently exploring the possibility of arranging designated colloquia in 2020 and 2021 on the issue of RRI benefits and impact pathways. Accordingly, we will collaborate closely with SuperMoRRI on the methodological challenges involved in this task.

Next Steps

This first version of the TRANSFORM Monitoring and Evaluation Guide provides analysis and overview, and can as such be considered as, metaphorically speaking, a menu of dishes and ingredients. During the next steps, the consortium will choose from this menu and co-create the actual choice of monitoring practices and indicators to be used in each region. These next steps will be taken in close and dialectical coordination with WP2 and WP3-5, that is, the WPs that design and execute the actions to be monitored and evaluated: In order to specify, say, how to use the place-based AREA framework, the concrete actions will have to be specified and planned somewhat more. None of these frameworks are likely to be used in their entirety; rather, criteria, variables and indicators will be selected from them. An important methodological point in these choices is that the underlying causal narrative and hence, the justification, of any particular criterion or indicator, should not be forgotten. In principle, any indicator can be used for any purpose; however, the question is with what quality, defined as its fitness for purpose.

In the course of tasks 7.1 and 7.2 we have been able to interact and consult with all partners at all clusters. However, it should not be denied that the COVID-19 pandemic has had consequences also for these tasks, in that the WP leader (the University of Bergen) has not been able to make site visits in the TRANSFORM regions. A high priority for WP7 is to perform such site visits as soon as possible in order to ensure the quality of the co-creation processes and obtain richer data on the actions to be monitored and evaluated. We will, however, continue to make contingency plans for a continued situation of extensive travel restrictions.

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This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under the grant agreement N° 872687

